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A Perspective on microneedle sensor arrays for continuous monitoring of the body's chemistry

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ABSTRACT

Recent advances in the field of microneedle devices are having an impact on both diagnostic and therapeutic approaches to sustaining healthy populations globally. Whether this is for improving drug and vaccine efficacy or for continuous sensing of key molecular indicators, the past five years have seen increased activity in both the academic and commercial sectors. In this Perspective, we focus on solid microneedle biosensors and discuss the advantages of these devices over alternative clinical diagnostic platforms as well as the technical challenges presented. We will emphasize how their use in continuous measurement of molecules *in vivo* is made possible with a minimally invasive technique that is simple to perform. This Perspective describes the function and current state of microneedle sensor arrays for the *in vivo* measurement of both endogenous molecules such as glucose and lactate and drugs such as penicillin.

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INTRODUCTION

Measurement of the composition of an individual's biofluids forms the basis of much contemporary clinical diagnostic science. The presence and concentration of biomarkers in blood or urine as well as less widely used fluids such as sweat or saliva can be highly informative.¹ More recently, monitoring of therapeutic drugs has gained increasing importance in personalizing treatments.² Whichever biofluid is analyzed, the aim is to link an analyte level (either biomarker or drug) to a pathological or physiological condition.

The information gleaned from discrete blood measurements is of course powerful and essential for many applications; however, in this traditional approach, samples are obtained through invasive and often labor-intensive means such as venepuncture. They require some medical training to reliably collect as well as laboratory instrumentation to analyze.³ Perhaps most importantly, information about time dependent changes in their concentrations are lost in the interval between collection and analysis. To improve upon discrete blood measurements, accuracy and precision must be maintained while increasing the density of data, increasing ease of use, and decreasing the level of invasiveness for the patient. Increased data density allows for an increased chance of detection of time dependant changes, important for optimized drug dosing in which a therapeutic window must be hit or biomarker monitoring in illness where changes in analyte

concentration may precede more serious outcomes. More easily obtainable data allow for monitoring to be performed in a greater range of scenarios, opening data acquisition to outside hospital settings, and lowering the time and expertise cost within hospitals and so lessening pressures on medical institutions. Acquiring required data in a less invasive manner from the patient is desirable from the point of view of the patient, who will want to experience the lowest amount of pain possible, and from the collector of the data who will likewise not want to inflict unnecessary suffering. This is especially important in certain patient populations such as neonates, who are challenging to draw blood from.

MONITORING IN INTERSTITIAL FLUID

The skin is the largest organ in the human body and fulfills multiple roles from preventing water and nutrient loss to providing a barrier against environmental assaults from microorganisms, toxins, and particulates. It is a self-renewing tissue composed of three primary layers: the epidermis, the dermis, and the hypodermis. The epidermis acts as a waterproofing layer and barrier to both ingress (infection) and egress (dehydration), and the dermis contains the blood and lymphatic vessels and pressure/pain sensing nerve cells which makeup the chemical, mechanical, and electrical connections between the skin and the internal organ systems. Finally, the hypodermis (or subcutaneous

tissue) is primarily a fatty layer that helps with thermoregulation, energy storage, and protection of deeper tissues.^{4,5} The fluid that bathes these tissues is called interstitial fluid (ISF) and forms a micro-circulatory system, whereby it diffuses through the capillary walls and is taken up by the lymphatic system. In contrast to blood, which is commonly drawn either by venepuncture or by a “fingerstick” drop of capillary blood, ISF may be accessed by penetrating only the very top layer of the epidermis, the stratum corneum. The stratum corneum is a layer of dead keratinocytes (corneocytes) and lipids that is the first barrier into the body through the skin. Under this layer, the viable epidermis (all other layers of the epidermis) is composed of various cell types and then beneath that the dermis with its capillary bed.

The concentrations of analytes in ISF are linked to their concentration in blood plasma.¹ Water and small polar molecules diffuse between the two compartments paracellularly, i.e., between the cells of the capillary wall while larger and/or more lipophilic molecules are transported transcellularly i.e., by uptake and secretion by the cells of the capillary wall. Transport into the ISF from plasma is increased by a pressure gradient generated by the continuous removal of ISF by the lymphatic system. Important biomarkers such as sodium, potassium, lactate, and glucose have concentrations that are similar between the two compartments. Non-protein-bound (“free”) levels for stress markers such as cortisol and for many drug molecules are also comparable, while protein bound molecules tend to remain in the plasma.⁶ This can be an advantage of ISF measurements, as non-protein-bound molecules often represent the active fraction of the drug/biomolecule in the body, and hence provide an assessment of their functional activity. In contrast, plasma levels are usually measured as total concentrations and typically require a separation step of free and bound to measure active concentration. Macromolecules such as small proteins or even antibodies have lower, but still significant ISF concentrations compared to plasma. Cytokines (typical masses 5–10 kDa) in ISF are typically 80% of blood plasma concentration, while antibodies (typical masses >100 kDa) are found at 15%–25% of the plasma concentration. ISF is, therefore, an excellent alternative to plasma in terms of the concentration of analytes for all but the largest molecules, with the not insubstantial benefit of lower concentrations of potentially interfering proteins such as albumin (ISF concentration is around 25% of that in plasma). Albumin typically binds to hydrophobic molecules of interest, thus reducing their free concentrations so lowering their sensitivity for sensing.¹

Several approaches to collecting and sampling ISF *ex vivo* have been proposed including reverse iontophoresis, hollow needle extraction, and microdialysis.⁷ These techniques are not suitable for continuous sensing; removal of the ISF for external analysis can cause the concentration of relevant molecules to change. For example, reverse iontophoresis causes paracellular electro-osmosis and so filters the plasma into the ISF more rapidly than would naturally occur if paracellular and transcellular pathways operated unperturbed. Microdialysis requires insertion of a needle and a hollow fiber under the skin, causing some discomfort and necessitating the wearing of a peristaltic pump and collecting discrete samples. Although not as invasive as blood sampling, it is more suited to research applications or critical care environments rather than routine continuous measurements. Sensing with *in situ* probes is, therefore, our preferred method and should have a suitable time resolution (minutes) for typical rates of change in concentration. Solid, coated microneedles that sense the analyte(s) without needing their extraction are minimally invasive and

provide continuous data without significantly perturbing the local analyte concentrations in ISF.

MICRONEEDLE SENSORS

Many approaches to making microneedles for sensing have been described in the literature, covering both materials, geometries, and fabrication methods. Microneedles are typically 300–1000 μm in length so that they pass through the stratum corneum and the viable epidermis but do not reach deep into the dermis/hypodermis (subcutaneous layer). They, therefore, avoid nerve endings, so cause little discomfort and sit bathed by the ISF. Pain and anxiety in patients have been shown to be low when using microneedles⁸ and although the majority of microneedle applications in the literature are concerned with the delivery of drugs and vaccines,^{9,10} there is no reason to think that similar effects will not be seen with microneedle sensors.

When coated with a thin (<200 nm) electrically conducting layer and functionalized with an analyte specific recognition element as well as possibly an outer (diffusion limiting) layer, microneedle sensors will respond to an analyte in the ISF without substantially affecting its concentration in the surrounding tissue.

Most of the published work to this point has utilized enzymes as the recognition element of solid microneedle sensors so the focus is in this area. Other recognition elements, such as aptamers or molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs), are beginning to be investigated and have significant advantages over enzymes, most notably, they can each be targeted toward any molecule of interest, whereas enzymes require specific substrates. Moreover, such synthetic receptors may both be more easily adapted to specific requirements (increase stability, raise or lower binding constant, adjust specificity against interferants). This Perspective focusses on microneedle sensors using enzymes as the recognition element, as such the examples presented here all suffer from the general disadvantages of using enzymes that may be overcome in future by an alternative technology. At present, enzymes are present in the device architectures most close to market.

Microneedles are straightforward to apply, much like a plaster, have a minimal risk of infection (following sterilization), and are less hazardous and easier to handle than a conventional hypodermic needle both in use and when disposed.⁸ A generic schematic of a solid coated microneedle sensing device is shown in Fig. 1. The mid-layer of the sensor contains an analyte specific molecule, which will elicit a local chemical change within the layer by reacting with the analyte. This chemical change is then converted at the transducing layer into an electrical signal.

The outer layer can serve several functions including protecting the sensing layer from degradation, protecting the tissues from the sensing layer (i.e., increasing device biocompatibility), and introducing an analyte mass transport/partitioning barrier that serves to change the apparent kinetic and equilibrium properties of the sensing molecules. This has the effect of shifting the sensor's signal output/analyte concentration response curves.

Information about changes in the concentration of molecules in ISF also has notable applications outside medicine.¹¹ Athletes may monitor biomarkers such as lactate, cortisol, or testosterone to increase the effectiveness of training.^{12–14} A simple and convenient wearable device that provides this information is expected to present opportunities with consumer potential. The financial drive of the sports performance market along with the medical need make convenient and

FIG. 1. Basic biosensing microneedle cross section (a), unfunctionalized microneedle patch (b), patch functionalized on three gold working electrodes (c), and two patches applied to an arm (d).

affordable biosensing devices an attractive area for research and investment.

FIRST GENERATION OXIDASE BASED SENSORS

The earliest and most extensively studied electrochemical biosensors are those based on oxidase or dehydrogenase enzymes.^{15–17} Oxidases catalyze the oxidation of target molecules by molecular oxygen with the latter's concomitant reduction to hydrogen peroxide (or in a few cases water). The hydrogen peroxide can then be electrochemically re-oxidized to oxygen at around 0.7 V (relative to a silver/silver chloride reference electrode), on a platinum or gold surface producing a current (two electrons for each hydrogen peroxide). A microneedle device with an immobilized oxidase poised at a suitable potential will, therefore, generate a current that is dependent on the concentration of the enzyme's substrate molecule. Two of the most common molecules measured this way are glucose and lactate, the former for its relevance to the management of diabetes and the latter for a range of applications, including medical (early warning of sepsis) and sports performance training. This combination of well-established bioelectrochemistry and a clear application focus led them being chosen as early exemplars of microneedle sensors. In a similar fashion, ethanol, through the action of alcohol oxidase, has been added to this list.¹⁸

Immobilization of the oxidase or, indeed, any sensing molecule with retention of its functionality on the surface of microneedle sensors is essential and much effort has been invested in this area.^{19,20} One common approach has been to entrap the relevant oxidase in an electrochemically generated polymer layer of either a conducting polymer such as poly(pyrrole) or a non-conducting one such as poly(phenol), reviewed by Cosnier.²¹ The latter approach has been applied to coating microneedle electrode sensors by inserting them in a solution containing phenol and glucose oxidase and applying a potential of 0.9 V. Alternative methods for immobilization on microneedles include adsorption or covalent attachment to the conducting layer, and entrapment in a hydrogel. Although oxygen is a ubiquitous oxidant for these enzymes, the potential required to reoxidize the hydrogen peroxide is high enough to introduce potential interference from physiological reductants such as uric acid and ascorbic acid, as well as common pharmaceuticals such as acetaminophen. To avoid this interference in these so-called “first generation” glucose sensors, low

potential redox shuttle molecules known as mediators have been employed in microneedle patches for both glucose and lactate, although not as yet *in vivo*.²² Where *in vivo* applications of these mediated (second generation) microneedle sensors are envisioned, the mediator will need to be held in close proximity to the sensing surface either in the form of a polymeric derivative or strongly adsorbed within the sensing layer.²³ The logical extension of this approach leads to “third generation” sensors where there is a direct electron transfer from enzyme to electrode so moving the operating potential close to the redox potential of the enzyme itself.

The glucose sensor with poly(phenol) entrapped enzyme was shown to respond in the range of 0–30 mM, where the physiological range in non-diabetic individuals is 4–7 mM and was tested in human volunteers as a proof of principle. No crosstalk between separate microneedle arrays on the same patch was observed, and the devices still functioned after sterilization (gamma irradiation) and storage at ambient temperatures for several days.

These early materials and methods used to make the microneedle sensors were time consuming and did not lend themselves to large scale production. After several iterations in the design and fabrication methods, microneedle sensor arrays were shown to be able to function continuously *in vivo* for both glucose and lactate measurements.^{24–27}

MICRONEEDLE SENSORS FOR DRUG MONITORING

While metabolite measurements are important in managing conditions such as diabetes or sepsis, microneedle sensor arrays have applications beyond these endogenous analytes and have recently been applied to therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM). Where drug-based treatments are used, it is often valuable to also measure the distribution and time dependent changes in drug concentrations that reflect both the drug's and patient's specific ADME (Adsorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion) characteristics (often referred to as the drug's pharmacokinetics and/or pharmacodynamics, PK/PD). A recent review has discussed the technology and benefits of near patient TDM and the use of microneedles in this regard has been illustrated with continuous penicillin monitoring.²

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a concerning and growing problem that may be somewhat mitigated through TDM. Minimizing the incidence of AMR demands precision dosing and use of selected

antibiotics. Moreover, some of the so-called “antibiotics of last resort” exhibit toxicity in humans. Biosensing of the concentration of an antibiotic *in vivo*, therefore, would be a useful tool for clinicians to ensure antibiotics are used in the most efficient manner, neither under nor over-used, while also avoiding potential adverse effects. Using a similar structure to the glucose and lactate sensing devices, a microneedle array was developed that responded to β -lactams such as phenoxymethylpenicillin orally dosed in healthy volunteers. In this example, it was a hydrolysis reaction that was monitored rather than an oxidation reaction, and this was achieved by coating the microneedles with a pH sensitive layer of iridium oxide (IrOx).^{28,29}

A schematic of an antibiotic sensing microneedle array is shown in Fig. 2. β -lactamase on the working electrode hydrolyzes amide bonds in β -lactam rings, resulting in the formation of amine and carboxylic acid groups (penicilloate plus proton). A decrease in the local pH caused by an increased concentration of acid within a β -lactamase containing hydrogel layer shifts the equilibrium between Ir^{III} and Ir^{IV} in the IrOx layer. This is transduced as a shift in the open-circuit potential (OCP) between the working electrode microneedle array and a Ag/AgCl reference electrode microneedle array. A control array is also present that is identical to the sensing one save for the absence of β -lactamase, nonspecific background is, thus, corrected for in the data.

FIG. 2. Schematic of the penetration of the β -lactamase modified microneedle array into the dermal-interstitial space (a) raw, unfiltered data (red, green, and blue) from three individual microneedle arrays on one patch, ISF penicillin concentration measured by microdialysis (blue), and plasma penicillin concentration measured from venous blood (b). Reproduced with permission from Gowers *et al.*, ACS Sens. **4**, 1072 (2019). Copyright 2019 American Chemical Society and Reproduced with permission from Rawson *et al.*, Lancet Digital Health **1**, e335 (2019). Copyright 2019 Authors, licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License. [(a) and (b), respectively].^{28,29}

As this is a pH dependant potentiometric measurement, a counter electrode is not required.

The microneedle arrays show an increase in OCP shortly after oral dosing of phenoxymethylpenicillin, slightly lagging and smaller than rises in serum levels but congruent with ISF levels obtained through microdialysis. Volunteers reported very little discomfort associated with the application and wearing of the device.

The devices were able to measure the changing concentration of penicillin in ISF, showing similar time dependent changes to the current gold standard microdialysis and to free drug in serum (analyzed by mass spectrometry). The devices yield continuous data and are substantially more comfortable to wear, easy to apply, and cheaper to produce than the alternatives.

CHALLENGES FOR MICRONEEDLE SENSORS

An important validation aspect of any emerging technology is how it compares to current gold standards. Blood plasma concentration levels for drugs and biomarkers are well established and widely used by medical professionals, whereas ISF concentrations are not immediately understood in the same way. However, the ISF levels are probably a closer representation of tissue concentrations, and therefore, could arguably be considered as more relevant.

Concentrations in ISF must, therefore, be reliable to and give a reliable indication of blood plasma concentrations for microneedle-based sensing if they are to be readily adopted. This relationship is an intrinsic aspect of the analyte. As discussed above, the concentrations are, indeed, often comparable especially for small to medium sized molecules (<1 kDa) but will need to be normalized if the ratio is not 1:1. It is also important to consider the effect of “ISF lag.” Most molecules of interest will pass from the blood plasma into the ISF (all molecules of interest that are not directly produced within skin tissue). The analyte may, therefore, be observed to rise first in the plasma, then in the ISF, which may cause their concentrations to lag in time and in some cases a perturbation of relative concentrations. This relationship is not linear, as the ISF concentration depends on both equilibration time between the compartments and the concentration in the blood which also changes over time, the result is that concentrations in the ISF are a “distorted mirror” rather than a simply delayed value from blood.³⁰ Both relative concentrations and their time dependencies must be understood if ISF measurements are to be as widely accepted as existing blood measurements.

In some cases, the chemical dynamics of molecules relevant for biosensing are well studied. Glucose, lactate, and some common drugs and biomarkers have been studied in ISF and related to blood plasma levels.^{1,31,32} Microneedle sensors may be developed to target many biomarkers, and we expect to see devices that sense such analytes as hormones in the near future, although it is feasible that any biomolecule present in ISF may be targeted. Whichever analyte is targeted, it is imperative that consideration is given to the difference, if there is one, between ISF and blood plasma concentrations.

A wide and varied array of enzymes are applicable for use in biosensing devices. When selecting an enzyme, as well as the parameters of specificity, turnover, and stability, the products of the enzymatic reaction must be suited to electrochemical, or other, sensing modalities. For oxidases, hydrogen peroxide is produced that is characteristically oxidized on platinum; for β -lactamases, a change in pH causes a shift in iridium oxide redox equilibrium. Whichever enzyme is used,

the products of a specific reaction must be able to be sensed electrochemically, either directly or indirectly.

One limitation of the oxidase/hydrogen peroxide approach is that at the working potential for hydrogen peroxide oxidation other endogenous and exogenous molecules are oxidized. Common examples include ascorbic acid (vitamin C) and glutathione. To avoid this problem, new enzymes are being developed, which exhibit direct electron transfer from enzyme to electrode, so they operate at lower potentials. This both reduces interference and avoids the depletion of oxygen at the electrode, a consequence of dermal tissue oxygen being typically lower than the co-substrates (typical oxygen concentration in the dermis is around 0.1 mM, glucose 4 mM, and lactate ≤ 2 mM).

Enzymes for every analyte of potential interest do not exist, and so alternatives are required. These could include nucleic acid and peptide aptamers, ligand binding proteins, particularly antibodies as well as synthetic receptors such as molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) and host-guest molecules. These alternatives may also overcome some other disadvantages of using enzymes, such as stability (both during fabrication of the microneedle sensors and their subsequent use), limited substrate range, and non-linear signal/concentration responses. While some of these disadvantages maybe overcome by engineering the enzymes' properties, it is our view that the use of a more diverse set of recognition molecules will be essential for the potential of microneedle technology to be fully realized.

Consideration should also be given to the conducting materials on the surface of the microneedles. Gold and platinum are excellent in this regard and find many uses throughout the literature, they are, however, expensive, both as a raw material and in their deposition methods. Carbon based microneedle coatings have been more challenging to produce but would dramatically lower expected costs for mass produced devices and may be more biocompatible. Outside of sensing applications, carbon microneedles have been used for vaccine delivery.³³ Acting as an agonist, the vaccine is delivered through the skin and its action is aided by an induced immune response caused by the microneedles themselves ("mechanical adjuvation").³⁴ As microneedle technology develops, organic electronic materials may replace the rigid metal and plastic elements used, resulting in a sensing patch with more flexibility and durability.^{35–37}

Microneedles that respond to an analyte without ISF extraction are minimally invasive and give continuous data without significantly changing the ISF composition. This is true with the proviso that the microneedles do not significantly damage surrounding cells so avoiding an increased immune and inflammatory response and resultant encapsulation of the microneedles. This will be a function of both the design of the microneedles and the biocompatibility of the material in contact with tissue. In the latter case, hydrogel coatings seem to yield good tissue integration.²⁸

While microneedles represent the sensing and transducing elements of a biosensor as well as its interface with skin tissue, to be an effective product supporting software and hardware must also be developed and integrated. Raw data (current, potential) must be converted to a usable format that is tailored to the specific use case. It is desirable for patient comfort to develop hardware such as wearable batteries, compact communication components, and miniaturized potentiostats that would allow for the microneedles to be worn as a wireless patch. This requires integration of batteries and communication systems that allow the patch to transmit to a display. Successful

integration of each component requires the cooperation of many areas of science and engineering, but if achieved will create a powerful new type of device to inform individualized medicine (www.elsah.research-project.at). Looking further ahead, the use of microneedle patches could move from simply passive sensing to active delivery entailing closed-loop control. In diabetes management, this is already implemented in a non-microneedle format and will require additional technological developments to integrate both these functions on a single wearable device.³⁸ Sampling in real time in a continuous fashion allows automation of dosages, a closed-loop system where drug delivery is controlled and measured without human interaction. This has the obvious advantage of automating a process that previously took time from medical staff but has the added benefit of ensuring even a narrow therapeutic window is constantly achieved rather than drug levels rising and falling over time when drugs are taken orally or intravenously as a bolus. This, in turn, may challenge the way that we currently think about pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics (PK/PD).

CONCLUSIONS

Microneedles have the capacity to provide direct, continuous measurement of the concentrations of endogenous and exogenous molecules in the ISF. Application and operation can be made straightforward and are inherently safe, production is scalable, and cost-effective. The analyte may be changed by varying the immobilized sensing molecule on the microneedle surface; enzymes, aptamers, or MIPs are possible candidates for this purpose. Continuous monitoring of drug concentrations and/or biomarker levels allows for truly individualized dosages and advice based on direct measurement of the body's own biochemistry.

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AUTHORS DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

A.E.G.C. is the founder of a company, Continuous Diagnostics Ltd., involved in commercialization of microneedle sensing devices.

Author Contributions

David Freeman: Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review and editing (equal). **Anthony Cass:** Funding acquisition (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – review and editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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